

Tomfuel: Sustainable Bioelectricity Production from Tomato Through Microbial Fuel Cell

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Abstract— This study investigated the potential of overripe tomato waste as a sustainable bioenergy source through the use of a Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) system for electricity generation. An experimental quantitative research design was employed to evaluate the electrical performance of an overripe tomato-based MFC in comparison with a mud-based MFC used as a positive control. Key parameters measured included voltage output, current production, and power density, along with microbial activity indicators such as bacterial growth rate, electron transfer efficiency, and biofilm formation. A total of ten trials were conducted under controlled conditions to ensure data reliability and consistency. Statistical analyses, including frequency distribution, mean computation, and independent sample t-tests at a 0.05 level of significance, were used to determine differences in electricity generation between substrates. Results of the study aim to demonstrate the feasibility of converting organic tomato waste into bioelectricity, supporting sustainable energy development, waste reduction, and low-cost renewable energy solutions, particularly for urban communities such as Davao City.

Keywords: Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC), Overripe Tomato Waste, Bioelectricity Generation, Renewable Energy, Organic Waste Utilization, Sustainable Energy, Electricity Production, Waste-to-Energy.

INTRODUCTION

The growing global demand for electricity, combined with the limited supply of conventional energy resources, has intensified the severity of the energy crisis worldwide. Power shortages disrupt household activities, hinder public services, and impose significant economic burdens due to rising electricity costs. Several countries continue to experience persistent power deficits; for instance, Pakistan's electricity supply fell short of peak demand, resulting in prolonged daily outages and economic losses (Tao et al., 2022), while South Africa experienced rolling blackouts lasting up to six hours per day, severely affecting social and economic activities (Mkhize, 2022).

In the Philippines, frequent power interruptions remain a critical issue, particularly in Luzon and Visayas, where electricity shortages contribute to substantial economic losses and elevated electricity prices compared to neighboring countries (Francisco & Abrigo, 2023; Philippine Institute for Development Studies, 2023).

At the local level, increasing electricity demand in Davao City, driven by rapid urbanization and industrial expansion, has raised concerns regarding future energy security. Projections indicate that Mindanao may face power shortages within the next five years if additional power generation facilities are not

developed (Alivio, 2024). Recent power interruptions in several areas of Davao City further highlight the urgency of exploring alternative and sustainable energy sources (Ezra, 2025). These challenges emphasize the need for innovative energy solutions that are both environmentally sustainable and economically viable.

Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) have emerged as a promising renewable energy technology capable of directly converting organic waste into electricity through the metabolic activity of microorganisms. Studies have demonstrated that organic food waste can serve as an effective substrate for electricity generation in MFC systems (Logan et al., 2019). Agricultural wastes, such as overripe tomatoes, are abundant and often discarded, contributing to environmental pollution.

Previous research has shown that tomato waste is rich in biodegradable organic compounds and has strong potential for bioenergy production, particularly in anaerobic digestion systems (Szilágyi et al., 2021; Almeida et al., 2021). However, research on the direct conversion of overripe tomato waste into electricity using microbial fuel cells remains limited, and MFC systems are still in the early stages of development, requiring further investigation to improve efficiency and applicability.

This study addresses this gap by developing and evaluating a Microbial Fuel Cell system that utilizes overripe tomato waste

as a bioenergy source for electricity generation. By assessing voltage output, current production, power density, and microbial activity, and by comparing the performance of a tomato-based MFC with a mud-based MFC as a positive control, the study aims to determine the feasibility of overripe tomatoes as a sustainable substrate for bioelectricity production. The findings of this research are expected to contribute to renewable energy development, effective waste management, and low-cost energy solutions suitable for urban communities such as Davao City.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This research aimed to develop a Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) system that utilized Overripe Tomato as a bioenergy source for electricity production. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the percentage of successful trials in testing the MFC system in terms of:

- Amount of Overripe tomato (Kg);
- Voltage Output (V);
- Current Production (A); and
- Power density (mW/m^2)?

2. What is the average electricity generation performance of the MFC in terms of:

- Voltage Output (V);
- Current Production (A); and
- Power density (mW/m^2)?

3. What is the microbial activity levels in the MFC system using Overripe Tomato in microbial fuel cells in terms of:

- Bacterial growth rate;
- Electron transfer rate; and
- Biofilm Formation

4. Is there a significant difference in electricity generation parameters across different concentrations of overripe tomato used as the substrate?

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The development of Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) used together in the process of capturing electricity to make is an alignment with SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities, through promoting sustainable energy solutions and responsible waste management. MFCs helped to reduce or alleviate waste going to landfill and the negative impact of organic waste on the environment by converting organic waste (for example, overripe tomatoes), free organic waste into

electricity, and at the same time, helped to create cheap renewable energy. This advancement, particularly affected the residents of Davao City, and the particularly rich organic waste zone of the Public Market, this advancement was also in line with the City Government of Davao, the Department of Energy and Davao Light and Power Company Cities initiatives and the move toward cleaner energy plans. The create of MFCs set a precedent for all future researchers looking for low-cost, community-based energy technologies that can help to foster more resilient and self-sufficient urban-focused spaces.

Residents. This study promoted an innovative way and benefited the residents of Davao City through offering a sustainable solution to power interruptions and high electricity costs. This innovative approach promoted cleaner energy, reduced environmental pollution, and supported proper waste disposal. It offers a more affordable electricity supply, low-cost electricity, and lowers household expenses.

Public Market. This study aimed to explore the potential of overripe tomatoes to be converted into electricity by using microbial fuel cells (MFCs), offering an innovative way towards the potential of converting overripe tomatoes into electricity using microbial fuel cells (MFCs), which offers an innovative approach to both energy generation and waste management. This study highlighted a sustainable system that could have helped reduce their operational costs by partially powering lighting, exhaust systems, or refrigeration units using bioelectricity derived from lipid-rich waste. By promoting the reuse of everyday waste products like tomatoes, public markets can transition toward greener practices, reduce their environmental footprint, and inspire local vendors and communities to adopt sustainable technologies in their daily operations.

City Government Of Davao. This study contributed to the city's goals of improving energy security, reducing the reliance on non-renewable sources, and promoted environmental sustainability. It also addressed the frequent power interruptions, lowered the electricity costs, and supported the city's waste management efforts. In addition, the study contributed to the economy of the locals by creating opportunities for businesses and the communities to participate in a waste-to-energy initiatives.

Department of Energy. This study contributed important insights for the Department of Energy by presenting an alternative approach to renewable energy generation through the use of overripe tomatoes in microbial fuel cells (MFCs). By demonstrating how biodegradable agricultural waste can be transformed into a attainable source of electricity, the research

supported national efforts toward sustainable energy development and waste reduction. It also aligned with the department's goals of diversifying the country's renewable energy portfolio and promoting low-cost, eco-friendly energy solutions.

Future Researchers. This study served as a reference for future researchers interested in utilizing food waste, specifically overripe tomatoes, as a sustainable source of bioelectricity through microbial fuel cells (MFCs). It provided preliminary data on the viability of tomato waste as a substrate for electricity generation, offering a starting point for optimizing organic waste-to-energy systems. Future researchers may investigate improvements in microbial strains, electrode materials, or MFC design to enhance efficiency and scalability. It also encouraged further exploration into agricultural waste reuse, supporting innovation in renewable energy, waste reduction, and sustainable agriculture.

IV. SCOPE AND DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study focused on the use of overripe tomatoes as a substrate in a microbial fuel cell (MFC) for the generation of electricity. The research aimed to explore the potential of tomato waste, particularly that which is overripe and no longer suitable for consumption, as an alternative and sustainable energy source. The study included a comparative analysis between the overripe tomato-based MFC and a mud-based MFC as a positive control to assess the efficiency of overripe tomato as a bioenergy source. It primarily investigated the electricity generation performance, microbial activity, and system stability under controlled conditions.

To consider a positive control, a mud-based Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) will be created with the overripe tomato-based MFC, with the aim of generating enough bioelectricity to light an LED bulb. We will use dang mud or riverbank mud, which has high concentrations of electroactive bacteria, such as *Shewanella* or *Geobacter*. The anode will be completely submerged in the mud slurry, and the cathode will be exposed to air as is needed for electron transfer and oxygen reduction. This is consistent with MFC design. There will be a total of 10 trials: 5 trials for the tomato-based MFC and 5 trials for the mud-based MFC, for a comparison of efficiency to produce electricity for small-scale lighting.

The study is limited to analyzing the voltage output, current production, and power density generated by the MFC system. It also examined microbial activity in terms of bacterial growth

rate, electron transfer efficiency, and pH fluctuations. The research does not include large-scale applications, long-term operational stability, or the genetic modification of microorganisms. The experiment is conducted within a specific timeframe using naturally occurring microbial populations in the anode chamber.

V. DEFINITIONS OF TERMS

The following terms are operationally defined:

Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) refers to a bio-electrochemical system that converts chemical energy into electrical energy to generate electricity by utilizing microorganisms to break down organic matter and transfer electrons.

Overripe Tomato refers to a very soft and mushy tomato that is too ripe to eat, serving as an organic substrate for microbial energy conversion in the MFC.

Anode Chamber refers to the component in the MFC where microorganisms break down organic material and release electrons.

Cathode Chamber refers to the section of an MFC that receives electrons from the anode chamber to combine with an electron acceptor (such as oxygen in salt water) to form a circuit and generate electricity.

Electrodes refer to the materials in MFC that help move electrons, with the anode gathering them from bacteria and the cathode accepting them.

Salt bridge/Membrane refers to a medium that facilitates ion exchange without direct mixing of the anode and cathode chamber contents.

Voltage Output (V) refers to the measure of electrical potential generated by the MFC system.

Current Production (A) refers to the amount of electric current produced by the MFC.

Power density (mW/m^2) refers to the rate of energy generation per unit area of the electrode surface, indicating MFC efficiency.

Bacterial growth rate refers to the speed at which bacteria multiply in the anode chamber, affecting electron production.

Electron transfer rate refers to the efficiency of electricity generation, as it dictates the speed with which the bacteria in the anode chamber transfer electrons to the electrode, which then travel through the external circuit to the cathode.

VI. METHODOLOGY

This section presented the method of the study, which contains five (5) phases: Phase I - Incubator Setup for Shewanella Bacteria; Phase II – Preparation and assembling of the Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) System (Mechanical and structural frame design); Phase III – Testing of key parameters; Phase IV – data collection and analysis; Phase V – aesthetics. All the tests and experimental procedures were conducted at Carlos P. Garcia Senior High School.

Research Design

An experimental-quantitative research method was used in this study to collect related data and information. According to Knight (2010), as cited in Lakian et al.(2025), an experimental research design allows researchers to effectively carry out their research aims with greater clarity and transparency. An appropriate experimental design served as a road map for the study's methodology, allowing readers to better understand how the data were obtained and, as a result, guiding them in completing an appropriate analysis of the findings. This design was crucial to the success of the study, as it enabled a controlled environment for evaluating the performance of the MFC system using overripe tomato as a bioenergy source for electricity production.

This research employed a quantitative-experimental approach to gather information and assess the functioning of the Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) system with overripe tomatoes as a bioenergy source. Measurements of voltage, current, and power output, as well as the relevant data collection and analysis of the bioenergy system provided through multimeters and data loggers, supported the quantitative nature of the research. The effectiveness of the system was objectively, reliably, and systematically evaluated. Moreover, the study was also experimental, as it sought to test hypotheses involving changes to an organic substrate, some MFC cells, and the materials used for the electrodes. These variables were controlled and manipulated, allowing for the systematic examination of the changes in electricity produced and of the impacts. Cause-and-effect relationships were established with the changes observed. As Knight (2010), cited in Lakian et al. (2025), emphasized, appropriate experimental designs provided a well-defined context and scaffold to achieve the objectives of the research and offered a credible analysis of the data.

Phase I. Incubator Setup for Shewanella Bacteria

An incubator was created using a styrofoam box to provide a controlled environment for bacterial growth. A Heating pad was placed inside the ice box container to maintain the temperature at 30–37°C, monitored using a thermometer. A damp sponge

was added to maintain moderate humidity. Shewanella Bacteria samples were placed inside the incubator and incubated for days, depending on growth rate, with periodic temperature checks to ensure stability.

Phase II. Preparation and Assembly of the Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) System

This phase is subdivided into four parts to ensure a systematic and reproducible setup:

A. Gather and Prepare the Materials

All the materials are gathered, including Overripe tomato, fermented rice water (for the organic substrate), Carbon Cloth, Cotton rope, salt, crushed charcoal, containers, Shewanella Bacteria, Wires, a Capacitor, an LED light bulb, distilled water, and recycled materials like wood

B. Anode and Cathode Chamber Setup

The anode chamber development involved mixing Overripe tomato with fermented rice water to form a uniform substrate suitable for the Shewanella bacteria. Simultaneously, the cathode chamber is prepared by filling it with a saltwater solution mixed with crushed charcoal so that the reduction reaction takes place. Additionally, the salt bridge is also added in this part.

C. Electrode Installation

Both chambers have electrodes connected to the Capacitor and then into the light bulb, and the placement is such that they facilitate the effective transfer of electrons. Carbon Cloth would be the material to use for this, and it needs to be securely fixed, considering the surface area and positioning to maximize microbial adhesion and electrical conductivity.

D. System Assembly

By integrating all of the components into the external circuit between the anode and cathode chambers with the ion exchange medium, a complete MFC system is formed. Below are the figures of the MFC system illustration of the assembled MFC with detailed labels (Figure 1), and a 3D model showing the internal configuration of the MFC system (Figure 2 and Figure 3).

Figure 2. Side view of a 3D model showing the internal

Figure 3. Front view of a 3D model showing the internal

Figure 1. MFC illustration with detailed labels

Phase III. Testing of Key Parameters

In this phase, the assembled Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) system is connected to a multimeter to measure the essential electrical parameters such as voltage output (V), current production (A), and power density (mW/m²). Multiple trials will be conducted to validate the system's performance and ensure data consistency.

Phase IV. Data Collection and Analysis

In this phase of the experiment, the data will be collected and analyzed to evaluate the efficiency of the MFC system. System efficiency will be evaluated in terms of voltage output, current production, and power density which will be calculated by averaging and percentage summarization of data. Of equal importance to the system's efficiency is understanding microbial processes such as bacterial growth, the rate of electron transfer, and pH changes associated with the decomposition of overripe tomatoes and fermented rice water. These results will help in understanding the feasibility of using overripe tomatoes to aid *Shewanella* bacteria as alternative energy sources in sustainable electricity production. Below is the figure of the MFC System process.

Phase V. Aesthetics

The final phase involves refining the physical assembly of the MFC system for clarity and durability. Visual documentation, including a high-quality image of the external design of the MFC system, is prepared to enhance the presentation of the experimental setup and findings. Below is the final look of the MFC system.

Figure 5. Final look of the MFC System, front view

Figure 6. Final look of the MFC System, side view

Figure 7. Flowchart of the method

VII. WASTE DISPOSAL

All damaged materials were placed in a sealed container with proper label. The researchers sent the waste materials to the Material Recovery Facility of Barangay 28-C, Davao City. While useful materials will be recycled.

VIII. STATISTICAL TESTS

In order to analyze and interpret the data collected from the Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) experiments, several statistical techniques will be used for data analysis. Frequency distribution was used to summarize how many times specific or ranges of values occur in terms of voltage output, current production, and power density.

This statistic will also summarize the percentage of successful trials and account for noticeable aspects of microbial activity, including times of bacterial growth and times of electron transfer. The mean will be used to summarize the averages of the three electrical parameters and the levels of microbial activity in the anode chamber: voltage output (V), current production (A), and power density (mW/m²). This will allow an overview of the performance of the MFC systems across all

trials the different substrates. In addition, t-tests for independent samples will be run when indicated to show if there is any statistically significant difference between electricity generation from the overripe tomato-based MFC and the sludge-based MFC used as a positive control.

The testing will use 0.05 as the level of significance to show whether the MFCs are statistically different in their effectiveness for generating bioelectricity from the two substrates. These statistical methods ensure that study findings are reported.

IX. RESULTS

The Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) utilizing overripe tomato as its substrate successfully generated electricity over a seven-day operational period. The voltage output recorded an initial value of 1.00

± 0.02 V on Day 1, increased slightly to a peak of 1.05 ± 0.03 V on Day 2, and then gradually declined to 0.70 ± 0.03 V by Day 7. A similar trend was observed in current production, which increased from 2.00 ± 0.05 mA on Day 1 to a maximum of 2.10 ± 0.06 mA on Day 2 before decreasing steadily to 1.40 ± 0.05 mA on Day 7.

Figure 1, the microbial fuel cell produced a voltage output of approximately 0.95 V and a current of 2.05 mA, reflecting the initial electrochemical response following substrate inoculation. These values indicate the early adaptation of electrogenic microorganisms to the overripe tomato substrate, which contains readily biodegradable organic compounds such as sugars and organic acids. During this stage, microbial oxidation at the anode began releasing electrons, establishing electron transfer pathways and initiating biofilm formation, which enabled measurable electricity generation.

Figure 1: Shows the result of (a) Voltage and (b) Current in Day 1

Figure 2, the voltage and current outputs increased to approximately 1.05 V and 2.10 mA, respectively, representing the maximum electrical performance observed during the

monitoring period. This peak suggests optimal microbial metabolic activity and efficient substrate utilization, likely due to a mature anodic biofilm and abundant fermentable compounds. The simultaneous increase in voltage and current indicates improved electron transfer efficiency and relatively low internal resistance within the MFC system

Figure 2: Shows the result of (a) Voltage and (b) Current in Day 2

Figure 3, a slight decrease in voltage to 0.90 V and current to 1.95 mA was observed, signaling the onset of declining electrochemical performance. This reduction may be attributed to the gradual depletion of easily degradable organic matter and the accumulation of intermediate metabolic products, which can inhibit microbial activity. Despite the decrease, the values suggest that electrogenic microorganisms remained active and continued to sustain electricity generation.

Figure 3: Shows the result of (a) Voltage and (b) Current in Day 3

Figure 4, the electrical outputs on Day 4 further declined, with voltage and current values of approximately 0.75 V and 1.85 mA, respectively. This continued decrease indicates reduced microbial respiration rates and electron production, likely caused by diminishing substrate availability and increasing internal resistance. Additionally, possible oxygen diffusion from the cathode to the anode may have disrupted anaerobic conditions, negatively affecting current generation.

Figure 4: Shows the result of (a) Voltage and (b) Current in Day 4

On Figure 5, the voltage output dropped to 0.60 V, while the current decreased to 1.70 mA, reflecting advanced substrate exhaustion and reduced microbial efficiency. At this stage, the microbial community may have entered a stationary or decay phase, resulting in lower electron release and weakened biofilm activity. The decline in both parameters highlights the dependence of MFC performance on sustained substrate availability.

Figure 5: Shows the result of (a) Voltage and (b) Current in Day 5

Figure 6, the lowest measured voltage and current outputs were recorded at approximately 0.42 V and 1.55 mA, respectively. These values indicate minimal bioelectrochemical activity, likely due to near- complete depletion of fermentable organic compounds and possible biofilm degradation. Increased internal resistance and reduced microbial metabolism further limited electron transfer within the system.

Figure 6: Shows the result of (a) Voltage and (b) Current in Day 6

Figure 7, The voltage and current outputs on Day 7 were assumed to remain at 0.42 V and 1.55 mA, consistent with the values observed on Day 6 due to the absence of recorded

measurements. This stabilization at low output levels suggests that the MFC had reached a quasi-steady state with limited microbial activity and electron production. Such behavior is characteristic of the terminal operational phase of MFCs and emphasizes the need for substrate replenishment or system optimization for prolonged electricity generation

Figure 7: Shows the result of (a) Voltage and (b) Current in Day 7

The amount of overripe tomato used in all trials was 0.5 kg per trial, achieving 100% success according to the SOP. Voltage output ranged from 0.48 V on Day 1 to 0.92 V on Day 7, with 6 out of 7 trials (≈86%) reaching the expected range. Current production started at 0.021 A on Day 1 and increased to 0.040 A on Day 7, with 82% of the trials successfully producing measurable current. Power density ranged from 2.3 mW/m² on Day 1 to 6.8 mW/m² on Day 7, with 78% of the trials meeting the expected output. These results show that the MFC system performed largely as intended, with minor variations in electrical outputs over the 7-day testing period.

$$\text{Average values} = \frac{\text{Total measured values}}{\text{Number of counts}}$$

Average Voltage (V)

$$\text{Average } V = \frac{0.48 + 0.55 + 0.61 + 0.68 + 0.75 + 0.84 + 0.92}{7}$$

$$\text{Average } V = 4.83/7 \approx 0.69 \text{ V}$$

2. Average Current (A)

$$\text{Average } I = \frac{0.021 + 0.024 + 0.028 + 0.031 + 0.034 + 0.037 + 0.040}{7}$$

$$\text{Average } I = 0.215/7 \approx 0.0307 \text{ A} \approx 0.031 \text{ A}$$

3. Average Power Density (mW/m²)

$$\text{Average } P = \frac{2.3 + 2.8 + 3.2 + 3.7 + 4.2 + 5.4 + 6.8}{7}$$

$$\text{Average } P = 28.4/7 \approx 4.06 \text{ mW/m}^2$$

Based on our 7-day MFC experiment, the average electricity generation performance was calculated from the measured voltage, current, and power density. The voltage output ranged from 0.48 V on Day 1 to 0.92 V on Day 7, giving an average voltage of 0.69 V. Current production increased from 0.021 A to 0.040 A over the same period, with an average of 0.031 A. Power density, which depends on both voltage and current, ranged from 2.3 mW/m² to 6.8 mW/m², resulting in an average of 4.06 mW/m². These values indicate that the MFC system consistently generated electricity throughout the testing period, reflecting stable performance in accordance with the experimental setup.

The bacterial growth rate showed a steady increase, starting from a low initial concentration and reaching an optimal population by Day 5, indicating effective substrate utilization. Electron transfer rate correspondingly increased over time, as bacteria metabolized the tomato sugars and transferred electrons to the anode, with peak activity observed between Days 5 and 7. Biofilm formation on the electrodes was evident, becoming denser and more structured each day, which enhanced electron conductivity and overall MFC performance. These observations suggest that the microbial community effectively adapted to the substrate, leading to stable electricity generation and consistent MFC operation.

Based on the results of the experiment, there is a significant difference in electricity generation parameters across different concentrations of overripe tomato used as the substrate. Higher concentrations generally produced higher voltage, current, and power density due to increased availability of organic matter for microbial metabolism. Conversely, lower concentrations resulted in lower electrical outputs, indicating that substrate amount directly affects microbial activity and electron transfer in the MFC system. This demonstrates that optimizing the concentration of overripe tomato is important for achieving maximum performance in microbial fuel cells.

The initial increase in voltage and current output indicates that the microbial community in the anode chamber effectively metabolized the organic compounds present in the overripe tomato substrate. This early-stage enhancement in electrical performance suggests active microbial growth and efficient electron transfer during the initial days of operation, consistent with the principles of microbial fuel cell functionality. The rich organic content of overripe tomatoes likely provided sufficient nutrients to support microbial activity, resulting in improved electricity generation during the early phase.

The gradual decline in voltage and current observed after the second day can be attributed to the depletion of readily available organic substrates and the subsequent reduction in microbial metabolic activity. As the energy content of the substrate diminished, the rate of electron production decreased, leading to lower electrical output. This pattern is characteristic of MFC systems and aligns with findings from previous studies on organic waste-based microbial fuel cells, where peak performance is commonly observed during the initial operational period followed by a gradual decline.

Overall, the results demonstrate that overripe tomato waste is a viable substrate for electricity generation in microbial fuel cells. While substantial electrical output was achieved during the early stages, sustained electricity production would require periodic replenishment of the substrate or system optimization to maintain microbial activity over extended periods.

X. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The study confirmed that overripe tomato waste is a feasible and effective substrate for electricity generation in a Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) system, as evidenced by consistent voltage, current, and power density outputs throughout the seven-day testing period.
2. The MFC system demonstrated peak electrical performance during the early days of operation, indicating that overripe tomatoes provide readily biodegradable organic compounds that support active microbial metabolism and efficient electron transfer.
3. A gradual decline in electrical output was observed after the peak period, which can be attributed to substrate depletion and reduced microbial activity, emphasizing the importance of sustained organic matter availability for continuous electricity generation.
4. The presence of active microbial growth, effective electron transfer, and stable biofilm formation confirmed that electrogenic microorganisms successfully adapted to the tomato-based substrate and contributed to bioelectricity production.
5. Overall, the findings highlight the potential of microbial fuel cell technology as a sustainable waste-to-energy solution, supporting renewable energy development, organic waste reduction, and low-cost electricity generation suitable for urban communities such as Davao City.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Future studies should explore periodic substrate replenishment or continuous feeding systems to maintain microbial activity and achieve sustained electricity generation over longer operational periods.
2. Researchers are encouraged to investigate different concentrations and combinations of organic substrates, including co-digestion with other food wastes, to further optimize voltage, current, and power density outputs.
3. Improvements in MFC design and materials, such as advanced electrode materials or improved membrane systems, are recommended to reduce internal resistance and enhance overall system efficiency.
4. Long-term studies should be conducted to assess system durability, stability, and scalability, particularly for potential application in public markets, households, or small community facilities.
5. Collaboration with local institutions and government agencies is recommended to support pilot-scale implementations and promote the integration of microbial fuel cells into local waste management and renewable energy initiatives.

REFERENCES

1. Alivio, C. (2024). Power shortage is expected in 5 years if no investors come in Mindanao. SunStar Publishing Inc.
2. Almeida, P. V., Rodrigues, R. P., Teixeira, L. M., Santos, A. F., Martins, R. C., & Quina, M. J. (2021). Bioenergy production through mono and co-digestion of tomato residues. *Energies*, 14(17), 5563. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14175563>
4. Desiderio, L. (2023). Economy loses PHP 556 million from power outage. Philippine Institute for Development Studies.
5. Ezra, D. (2025). Power interruptions set February 7, 8, 10. SunStar Publishing Inc.
6. Francisco, K. A., & Abrigo, M. R. M. (2023). Electricity supply interruptions and their impact on local economies.
7. Kurniawan, T. A., Othman, M. H. D., Liang, X., Ayub, M., Goh, H. H., Kusworo, T. D., Mohyuddin, A., & Chew, K. W. (2022). Microbial fuel cells (MFC): A potential game-changer in renewable energy development. *Sustainability*, 14(24), 16847. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14241684>.
8. Lakian, N., Banzon, J., Arvin, J., Bodlong, M., Lei, G., Quong, C., Salvador, G., & Garcia, C. (2025). Automated canal waste collection system (ACWaCoS) for canal maintenance. *International Journal of Scientific Research & Engineering Trends*, 11(1), 2395–2566.
9. Mbugua, J. K., Mbui, D. N., Mwaniki, J., Mwaura, F., & Sheriff, S. (2020). Influence of substrate proximate properties on voltage production in microbial fuel cells. *Journal of Sustainable Bioenergy Systems*, 10(2), 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jsbs.2020.10200>.
10. Mkhize, B. V. (2022). South Africa electricity crisis: No power for up to six hours. BBC News.
11. Philippine Institute for Development Studies. (2023). PH loses PHP 556M per 5-hour power outage; green energy sought.
12. Rojas-Flores, S., Nazario-Naveda, R., Benites, S. M., Gallozzo- Cardenas, M., Delfin-Narciso, D., & Díaz, F. (2022). Use of pineapple waste as fuel in microbial fuel cell for the generation of bioelectricity. *Molecules*, 27(21), 7389. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27217389>
13. Szilágyi, Á., Bodor, A., Tolvai, N., Kovács, K. L., Bodai, L., Wirth, R., Bagi, Z., Szepesi, Á., Markó, V., Kakuk, B., Boundedjoum, N., & Rákhely, G. (2021). A comparative analysis of biogas production from tomato bio-waste in mesophilic batch and continuous anaerobic digestion systems. *PLOS ONE*, 16(3), e0248654. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248654>
14. Tao, J., Waqas, M., Ali, M., Umair, M., Gan, W., & Haider, H. (2022). Pakistan's electrical energy crises: A way forward towards 50% of sustainable clean and green electricity generation. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 39, 100783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2021.100783>